

Multi-method Approach with Fisherwomen in Tokou Village, Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025.

Study report

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1. Introduction to the project and research context

Reef passages are natural breaks in reefs that connect the coastal zones to the open ocean. As hotspots for biodiversity reproductivity, and as pathways for fisher(wo)men as well as a variety of non-human species, they hold remarkable value for environment and society.

The project SOCPacific2R designs its research activities using an empirical inter- and transdisciplinary approach, combining natural and social sciences methods, and focuses on reef passages in Fiji and New Caledonia. The project aims to:

1. Conducting a transdisciplinary study of reef passages as under-researched features of social-ecological coral reef systems that constitute complex, interconnected, and dynamic assemblages of living and non-living, dwelling and transiting, entities that interact with each other;
2. Documenting both area-based and other management and conservation arrangements applied to reef passages, including the pros and cons that local stakeholder groups identify;
3. Establishing a participatory science-society-policy dialogue informed by social-ecological studies, Oceanian socio-cosmologies and sovereignties, and governance norms in/for the management and conservation of reef passages.

SOCPacific2R works with various stakeholders to achieve the project's goals: scientists, administrators, NGOs, and local communities. The outcomes of the project will feed into wider frameworks on marine sustainability such as the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Local communities are the main knowledge holders and users of the reef passages that surround the Fijian and New Caledonian islands. The presented study aimed to learn their perspectives and experiences concerning the reef passages on Ovalau island in Fiji through an interdisciplinary research team, and was conducted by a student group of the University of the South Pacific (USP) between September 2025 and February 2026.

2. Research Methodology

Four complementary research methods were used during data collection with fisherwomen in Tokou Village, Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025: semi-structured interviews, participant observation, drawings, and participatory mapping (fig. 1). Semi-structured interviews with fisherwomen were the primary method, providing the foundation for the research and allowing for in-depth information to be gathered. Drawings added a visual dimension, enabling the fisherwomen to express ideas and information that could not be fully captured through interviews alone. Participant observation complemented both interviews and

Figure 1: Timeline of applied methods in this study.

drawings by showing in real time what was described or illustrated, helping in understanding locations and fishing practices more vividly. This also helped in fostering trust and rapport with the participants, encouraging more detailed responses. Participatory mapping further supported the interviews by allowing the women to quickly and easily pinpoint their favourite fishing locations, providing a clear visual and spatial representation of their fishing grounds. Overall, while each method was valuable on its own, the combination of all four provided richer and more reliable data than any single method could achieve. Free prior and informed consent (FPIC) was used for all methods.

Table 1: Participating fisherwomen in Tokou village.

Women interviewed	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Age	10 - 19		20 - 29	30 - 39	40 - 49		60 - 69		80+		
Interview 1						X	X			X	X
Interview 2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Drawings (with Interview 2)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Interview 3	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X
Participatory Mapping (with Interview 3)	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X
Participant observation				X			X	X			

2.1 Semi-structured Interviews

A total of 23 semi-structured interviews were conducted with a total of 11 interviewees across three periods of fieldwork between September 2025 and February 2026 (Table 1). The first phase (n = 4) included four fisherwomen. The second phase comprised 10 interviews (n = 4 follow-up; n = 6 new) involving 11 fisherwomen (as an interview was conducted with two people simultaneously), while the final phase (n = 9 follow-up) focused on in-depth follow-up sessions with 9 fisherwomen. Participants ranged in age from teen to old age, providing an intergenerational perspective on reef passages and fishing knowledge.

Interviews lasted between 30 and 120 minutes and were held in participant-selected locations, such as homes and community halls, to ensure accessibility and minimize disruption (Kitolelei et al., 2022). Conversations were conducted in Fijian and English, audio-recorded with consent, and supplemented by detailed field notes.

Participants were identified through purposive sampling and community-based recruitment, guided by the *Roko Tui Tokou* (chief of Tokou Village) and community recommendations to locate key knowledge holders. This expert-led approach is standard for documenting detailed, place-based, traditional ecological knowledge (Singh et al., 2025).

An interview guide (Attachment01) was developed around six thematic domains: **(1) personal history and fishing involvement, (2) fishing practices and spatial usage, (3) cultural knowledge, totems, and sacred oral histories, (4) seasonal knowledge and species observations, (5) environmental change and species rarity, and (6) women's roles in environmental stewardship and participatory mapping** (see Appendix). Using open-ended questioning enabled the documentation of nuanced Indigenous narratives and lived fishing experiences (Kitolelei et al., 2022).

The data were analyzed using a qualitative, inductive, descriptive, and manual approach. A thematic analysis was conducted, identifying key themes across the interviews, through careful and repeated reading and review of my interview notes (rather than software-based coding). Key patterns and insights from the interviews were compared according to the age of the interviewees.

The first six interviews were analyzed and organized using Excel, where the data were categorized by interview questions. Each column contained one question with the responses from each interviewee in each line. However, the responses from the remaining participants were not organized in the same way, meaning the other 17 interviews were left unstructured in this particular format (further analysis could be done at a later stage).

2.2 Participant observation

Participant observation was carried out through four fishing trips in Tokou Village's waters across two phases of fieldwork. One trip took place during the first phase (September - October 2025) with a fisherwoman, her brother, and her granddaughter. The other three trips were done during the second phase (November - December 2025) with two

fisherwomen and several boys and men from Tokou Village. Most trips happened during the day and sometimes continued into the late afternoon or early evening.

During these trips, we observed and participated in fishing activities. This created opportunities to learn directly from fisherwomen about their fishing practices, fishing grounds, reef navigation, the types of fish they caught, their relationship with the fish and sea, and caring practices towards other fisherwomen on the boat and juvenile fish. Some trips lasted up to six hours, which allowed enough time to see the full fishing process from preparation to completion. Being present on the fishing trips also allowed informal conversations where additional insights were shared that did not always come up during interviews.

Participant observation was used because it allows researchers to engage with everyday practices in their natural setting and notice things that may not emerge through formal interviews alone (Oliver de Sardan, 2015). Taking part in the fishing helped me to better understand techniques, decision-making, and traditional and local knowledge that are learned through practice.

This method was also important because much of the knowledge involved in fishing is tacit, meaning people may find it difficult to fully explain their skills and decisions in words. By observing and participating in fishing activities, I was able to capture these practical and embodied forms of knowledge that would likely be missed if the study relied only on interview data (Zahle, 2012).

Overall, participant observation helped me to understand how reef passages and other fishing grounds are used in practice, why and when certain areas are chosen, and the importance of these spaces to fisherwomen's daily lives and livelihoods. It also provided insight into the skills, experiences, and knowledge involved in being a fisherwoman in Tokou Village.

Participant observation was analyzed through reflections, memories, photo collage and key notes recalled from the fishing trips. This involved reflecting on the places visited for fishing, the fishing gear and bait used, the types of fish caught, and the amount of time spent at sea. Pictures and videos were also used during these trips to document key moments. Attention was also given to the atmosphere on the boat and the fisherwomen's relations on the boat between themselves, the fish, and the sea. This also included whether the fisherwomen appeared to enjoy themselves, their emotional responses, the additional gear they brought, and specific practices that were better understood through demonstration. Observations also included where they positioned themselves on the boat and general knowledge shared about their fishing grounds and reef passages. These observations were then compared with what was described by participants during their interviews, in drawings and during the participatory mapping.

2.3 Drawings

Drawings were used as a visual method during the second phase of fieldwork, alongside the interviews. Following the approach suggested by Brailas (2020), participants/fisherwomen (n = 10) were invited to draw during the interviews (Table 1). The fisherwomen were asked to sketch their fishing grounds and the practices they used near reef passages like Nalulu and Gavo. This helped to capture "tacit" knowledge - things that the women know and do every day but might find difficult to explain clearly in words alone.

In total, ten drawings were produced (Attachment02, from a presentation of results to the community). While eleven women were interviewed, one declined, and a few others felt a bit shy or hesitant, saying they "did not know how to draw." Brailas (2020) explains that this is common for adults who are not used to drawing, but he notes that the actual process of trying to draw helps people remember feelings and experiences more deeply. By reassuring them that the artistic quality did not matter, we were able to collect rich visual information that showed how they understand, navigate, and experience the sea and reef passages in their daily lives.

All ten drawings were carefully reviewed to identify recurring patterns and key features represented by the women. This included noting how often reef passages were drawn, which specific passages were shown, the types of fish species illustrated, physical marine features included, the fishing activities depicted, and whether fishing was represented as taking place individually, in pairs, or in groups, and if the women were including themselves in the drawings and how.

2.4 Participatory Mapping

In addition, participatory mapping was carried out during the last phase of fieldwork (in February 2026) with fisherwomen from Tokou Village, who had previously taken part in interviews. The mapping activity was used alongside follow-up interviews as a visual guide to help participants explain and represent their spatial knowledge more clearly. The session took place in Tokou's community hall and involved nine participants (Table 1).

During the activity, fisherwomen were asked to identify and map their two to three main fishing locations by placing stickers on printed maps focusing on Nalulu Passage and Gavo Passage. These

Figure 2: Summary Map of Interviews, Drawings and Participant Observation used in the Participatory Mapping session. Map by Auréa Pottier.

summary maps (fig. 2) were developed by us based on the outcome from previously conducted methods, and were used to correct, clarify and add information. While drawing their fishing grounds on the map, these fisherwomen described their fishing practices used in the past and present, and the types of fish commonly caught there. Notes were taken during the activity to capture participants' explanations and additional contextual information.

Some participants also used chalk markers (dots) to show the edges and boundaries of reef passages (*batini daveta*). This helped document detailed spatial knowledge that is not always easily explained through interviews alone. For example, the side of the reef passages and the middle of the passages.

Participatory mapping was analyzed using a previously developed summary map (based on interview data and drawings) of fishing practices and locations. Through repeated review, it became clear which locations were participants' main fishing areas, particularly their top two to three fishing spots. These spots were different for each of the fisherwomen. Some were close to each other, with others having some distance between them. The above-mentioned earlier summary map was thus revisited to ensure it accurately reflected participants' fishing practices and locations.

In this way, the maps we produced initially served as a draft visual representation of interview data, then allowed confirmation and corrections by fisherwomen themselves where needed. Overall, most of the previously mapped practices and locations were found to closely match participants' explanations. However, a few corrections were made to some of the fishing spots since they now pinpointed their fishing location and some new spots were also highlighted on the map, such as fishing outside of Nalulu Passage.

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